

Fast profiling of primary, secondary, conjugated, and sulphated bile acids in human urine and murine feces samples

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Abstract

Bile acids (BAs) are a complex class of metabolites that have been described as specific biomarkers of gut microbiota activity. The development of analytical methods allowing the quantification of an ample spectrum of BAs in different biological matrices is needed to enable a wider implementation of BAs as complementary measures in studies investigating the functional role of the gut microbiota. This work presents results from the validation of a targeted ultra-high performance liquid chromatography – tandem mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS) method for the determination of 28 BAs and six sulphated BAs, covering primary, secondary, and conjugated BAs. The analysis of 73 urine and 20 feces samples was used to test the applicability of the method. Concentrations of BAs in human urine and murine feces were reported, ranging from 0.5 to 50 nmol/g creatinine and from 0.012 to 332 nmol/g, respectively. 79% of BAs present in human urine samples corresponded to secondary conjugated BAs, while 69% of BAs present in murine feces corresponded to primary conjugated BAs. Glycocholic acid sulphate (GCA-S) was the most abundant BA in human urine samples, while tauro lithocholic acid was the lowest concentrated compound detected. In murine feces, the most abundant BAs were α -murocholic, deoxycholic, dehydrocholic and β -murocholic acids, while GCA-S was the lowest concentrated BA. The presented method is a non-invasive approach for the simultaneous assessment of BAs and sulphated